

Optimization of Time Modes of Neutron Activation Analysis of Natural Media Samples

Author(s), M.HOSHUMHUJAEV¹,

And

SH. IMOMKULOV²

Abstract:

The time modes of neutron activation analysis of samples of natural environments were experimentally optimized based on the nuclear-physical characteristics of the studied and "interfering" radionuclides. The detection limit and the accuracy of element detection were chosen as criteria for optimizing the method. The analysis of metrological parameters of neutron activation analysis allowed us to conclude that the detection limit is low, reproducibility is satisfactory and correctness is correct, which favors the use of the method in quality control of various natural environments.

Keywords: objects of the natural environment, atmospheric aerosols, environmental pollution, neutron activation analysis, optimization of time modes, determination limit, gamma radiation, gamma spectrometry, half-life, radionuclide activity, element isotope, analysis error, radioactive decay, analytical peak, determination accuracy, statistical error, photo peak area, "interfering" radionuclides,

EASIJ

Accepted 10 August 2020
Published 15 August 2020
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3987386

About Author

Author(s): M.HOSHUMHUAJEV¹, SH. IMOMKULOV²

¹Associate Professor, the Department of " Decorative gardening and landscaping", Namangan engineering technology institute.

E-Mail: madaminxojaxoshimxojaeyv@mail.ru

²Assistant Professor, the Department of "General technical disciplines", Namangan engineering technology institute.

E-Mail: shuhrat19801221@mail.ru

1. Introduction

In modern conditions of rapid industrial development, urban growth and development of new areas, the impact of human activities on the environment is increasing. Protecting the environment from pollution is one of the most important issues of our time. Getting into the air, water and soil, toxic chemicals pose a real threat to human, plant and animal life on our planet. This, in turn, leads to the need for systematic monitoring of the content of pollutants of anthropogenic and technogenic origin in the atmosphere, natural waters, and soils.

2. Materials and Methods

Various chemical, physical and physico-chemical methods are currently widely used to study the composition of objects in the natural environment: spectral, atomic absorption, electrochemical, x-ray-fluorescent, mass spectrometric, neutron activation and other methods.

Neutron activation analysis (NAA) stands out among the mentioned advantages:

a) high sensitivity (many elements of the periodic table can be defined within 10^{-3} - 10^{-8} %);

b) independence from the chemical composition of the analyzed sample and the forms of finding elements in it;

c) the simplicity of the spectra of gamma radiation of the excited nuclei, in contrast to spectral and x-ray methods;

d) sufficiently high accuracy, depending, as a rule, only on the accuracy of the preparation of the standard;

e) multi-element analysis capability and high performance.

The choice of NAA as a method of analysis is also determined by the problem statement, which provides for the determination and comparative study of the elemental composition of several objects of the natural environment - atmospheric aerosols and precipitation, soil and river water. The contents of the studied elements in each of these media are usually low, and quite different from each other [1]. The NAA appears to be the most suitable for this task.

In table.1. analytical parameters of the most common physical and chemical methods for analyzing natural objects are presented [2]. As follows from the data in table 1. among the methods of analysis, the most favorable analytical parameters are nuclear physical methods, in particular, NAA. Consequently, the NAA has been widely used in monitoring the quality of almost all environmental objects in recent years.

Table 1. Limits of determination of various analytical methods [2].

Methods	Limit of determination, g	Sample volume, ml	Concentration mol/l
Classical method	10^{-6}	10	10^{-6}
Special ultra micro methods	10^{-12}	0.001	10^{-8}
Absorption spectrophotometry	10^{-8}	0.01	10^{-7}
Inversion polarography	10^{-10}	10	10^{-10}
Mass spectrometry	10^{-12}	0.01	10^{-9}
Gas chromatography	10^{-13}	0.001	10^{-9}
Atomic absorption spectrometry	10^{-13}	0.01	10^{-10}
Substoichiometric method			

isotope dilution	10^{-11}	1	10^{-10}
Neutron activation analysis	10^{-13}	1	10^{-12}

NAA is based on the reaction of radiation capture of thermal neutrons by nuclei. Identification of a radionuclide in a mixture is carried out by the type and energy of radiation and the half-life. After removing the gamma spectrum, it identifies the photo peaks of the nuclide to be determined, and calculates its area, which is directly proportional to the activity of the radionuclide.

NAA is used in two versions-instrumental and with radiochemical isolation. Instrumental neutron activation analysis (INAA), which is used by us, is based on gamma-ray spectrometry using scintillation or semiconductor detectors. INAA is characterized by high performance, relatively low labor intensity, multi-element, and the ability to automate analysis [3]. The sensitivity of the method is mainly determined by the intensity of the neutron flux, the reaction cross-section, the natural distribution of the isotope, and the output of gamma quanta. Under equal irradiation conditions, the sensitivity of the method is greater for an element with a lower atomic mass and a relatively high distribution of the element's isotope. The half-life does not matter for the sensitivity of the method, except for long-lived radionuclides, when the irradiation time is significantly less than the half-life.

The INAA error consists of the following components: errors related to irradiation processes (self-absorption, shielding, neutron flux gradient), repackaging after irradiation, measurements (related to geometry, miscalculations, instability of equipment, etc.), the statistical nature of radioactive decay and reference. The INAA specificity of environmental samples most often excludes errors associated with self-absorption and self-shielding of neutrons in samples. It can be shown that the analysis error is mainly determined by [4] statistical measurement error.

$$s_{ct} = [I_n + 2I_f]^{1/2} / N_n \quad (1)$$

where, I_n - area of the analytical peak of the defined element,

I_f - background area under the analytical peak.

The concentration of elements is determined by the formula

$$C_{xi} = [I_{samp.} \cdot m_{ref.i}] / [I_{ref.i} V], \quad (2)$$

where, C_{xi} - concentration of the i -th element;

$I_{samp.}$ - the area of the analytical peak of the i -th element in the breakdown;

$m_{ref.i}$ - mass of the i -th element in the comparison sample;

$I_{ref.i}$ - the area of the analytical peak of the i -th element in the comparison sample;

V - the volume of pumped water or air, or mass of the soil.

Using the example of analysis of atmospheric aerosols, we will consider the optimal scheme of INAA. The task of optimizing the time modes of analysis is to identify such conditions of INAA that provide simultaneous determination of the content of the maximum number of elements with the lowest error. There are theoretical and experimental ways to optimize INAA time frames [5]. Methods for optimizing the INAA of natural samples are reduced to the study of some functions and are based on the solution of the following equation:

$$a = f(\bar{x}, \bar{p}, \bar{q}) \quad (3)$$

where, a -optimization function (detection limit, error, etc.);

$\bar{x}$ -a set of optimized parameters-factors (time of irradiation, cooling, and measurement);

$\bar{p}$ - a set of nuclear physics data determined by the sample matrix (mass of isotopes, their atomic weights, reaction cross-section, decay constants, etc.);

$\bar{q}$ - a set of characteristics of the analytical complex equipment (intensity of activating radiation, efficiency of registration of the equipment, etc.). as a rule, due to the complex nature of the function (3), optimization of the analysis conditions is carried out on an electronic computer (computer) or experimentally.

Optimization of time modes of analysis was carried out by us experimentally, based on the nuclear-physical characteristics of the studied and interfering radionuclides. The limit of detection and accuracy of element detection were chosen as the criteria for INAA optimization. The proposed optimal scheme of INAA on the example of atmospheric aerosols is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. INAA Scheme of urban atmospheric aerosols

Many works [5,6] on optimization of time modes of INAA have been published in the literature. where multiple irradiations, "cooling" and measurement are suggested. In our case, it was necessary to conduct a highly sensitive mass analysis for a certain number of toxic anthropogenic and natural elements in a large number of samples. At the same time, high productivity, low cost and the ability to determine the content and form of finding the necessary range of elements from a single sample (atmospheric aerosols, precipitation and water suspensions) are important.

It should be emphasized that thanks to the automation of the aerosol sampling process, we were able to gain relatively high weights on the filters, which in turn influenced the INAA method of atmospheric aerosols, namely, the measurement time of long-lived isotopes was reduced by 2.5-3 times with an increase in the number of detected elements and a decrease in the error of analysis. Thus, the productivity of the method was significantly increased and the cost of a single analysis was reduced, which is very important when analyzing a large number of samples.

3. Results and Discussion

Determination of Mo, Sm, Au and As in soils and the dissolved phase of water is difficult due to the "interfering" activity of ^{24}Na and ^{82}Br . To increase the sensitivity and accuracy of determining these elements, we resorted to varying the neutron spectrum. It is known that the activation cross section of some elements has a resonant character over the thermal region of the neutron spectrum [5]. When irradiated in a nuclear reactor, a cadmium filter suppresses the flow of thermal neutrons at the sample location and activation will be carried out by resonant neutrons of a wide spectrum of energy. These elements were determined by irradiating the test sample in the cadmium channel for 5 hours in the flow $f = 5 \cdot 10^{13}$ neutron $\text{cm}^{-2}\text{sec}^{-1}$. After "cooling" for 6 days for medium-living and 20 days for long-lived radionuclides, measurements were made on the corresponding gamma lines on a unit containing two spectrometric paths with Ge (Li) detectors of 80 cm^3 and a mini-computer ISKRA-226 using the SOSNAA program [7], developed by employees of the activation analysis laboratory of the Institute of Nuclear physics of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The resolution of the instrument in the ^{60}Co peak region (1332.5 Kev) was 3.2 Kev.

The nuclear-physical characteristics [8] of the elements we define are given in table.2. Mathematical processing of the obtained spectrometric information included spectrum smoothing, automatic peak search, determination of the areas of photo peaks and background, and calculation of the statistical error of determination.

Figure 2-5 shows some characteristic gamma-spectra of the samples of natural environment objects that we have studied. The superimposition of gamma lines of various radionuclides leads to difficulties in interpreting spectroscopic information. Such difficulties occurred in the case of the following radionuclide pairs: ^{134}Cs - ^{124}Sb , ^{153}Sm - ^{239}U , ^{65}Zn - ^{46}Sc , ^{203}Hg - ^{75}Se , ^{46}Sc - $^{110\text{m}}\text{Ag}$ и ^{85}Sr - ^{65}Zn . In the first case, we did the following.

Fig. 2. Gamma spectrum of atmospheric aerosol: $\tau_{irrad.} = 5$ hours; $\tau_{cool.} = 6$ days; $\tau_{measur.} = 200$ sec.

Fig. 2. Gamma spectrum of atmospheric aerosol: $\tau_{irrad.} = 5$ hours;

Fig. 4. Gamma spectrum of the dissolved phase of river water: $\tau_{irrad.} = 5 \text{ hours};$
 $\tau_{cool.} = 20 \text{ days}; \tau_{measur.} = 400 \text{ sec.}$

Fig. 5. Gamma spectrum of soil: $\tau_{\text{irrad.}} = 3 \text{ hours}$; $\tau_{\text{cool.}} = 20 \text{ days}$; $\tau_{\text{measur.}} = 200 \text{ sec}$.

Table 2. Nuclear-physical characteristics of radionuclides to be determined [8]

Defined element to be	Measured radionuclide	Period half-life		Analytical line, Kev
Na	^{24}Na	15	Hour	1368.6
K	^{42}K	12	Hour	1524.7
Sc	^{46}Sc	83.8	Day	889.3
Cr	^{51}Cr	27.7	Day	320.1
Fe	^{59}Fe	44.5	Day	1099.2, 1291.6
Co	^{60}Co	5.27	Year	1173.2, 1332.5
Zn	^{65}Zn	244	Day	1115.6
As	^{76}As	1.1	Day	559.1, 657
Se	^{75}Se	120	Day	264.6, 279.5
Br	^{82}Br	1.47	Day	776.5, 554.3
Sr	^{85}Sr	64.8	Day	514.0
Mo	^{99}Mo	2.8	Day	140.5, 180
Cd	^{115}Cd	2.23	Day	336.3
Sb	^{124}Sb	60.2	Day	602.7, 1691

Cs	¹³⁴ Cs	2.05	Year	605.0, 795.8
La	¹⁴⁰ La	40.2	hour	1596.5, 487
Sm	¹⁵³ Sm	1.94	Day	103.2
Eu	¹⁵² Eu	13.6	Year	344.3, 1408
Au	¹⁹⁸ Au	2.69	Day	411.8
Hg	²⁰³ Hg	46.6	Day	279.2
Th	²³³ Pa	27.0	Day	311.9
U	²³⁹ Np	2.36	Hour	228.2, 277.6

Although the line ~ 603 Kev has almost one hundred percent gamma-quantum yield as for ¹³⁴Cs, so for ¹²⁴Sb, we used clean lines to determine these radionuclides 796 Kev and 1691 Kev with lower gamma-quantum yields (30% and 50% respectively), which was quite enough with our samples. In other cases, where the second radionuclide in each pair was interfering with the first, the ratio of the two characteristic lines of the second radionuclide in its reference was used for determination of its contribution to the total peak with the first radionuclide in the test sample. The contribution of the second radionuclide found in this way was subtracted from the specified peak to determine the contribution of the first.

For sampling aerosols, various filters made of organic material, the main components of which are C, O, H and N, are preferred, since they are not activated by thermal neutrons and should not create an interfering background when determining elements. However, during manufacturing and storage, filters can be contaminated with impurity elements, which determine the detection limits of the method.

The "purity" of the filters used was studied using INAA. In table.3 the results of analysis of the content of impurity elements in some filters and packaging material - polyethylene are presented. The results of the analysis showed that the content of impurity elements can vary from batch to batch and depending on the conditions and storage time of filters. Therefore, it is desirable to analyze simultaneously "unexposed" filters from the same batch. Before packing the samples, plastic bags were treated with concentrated nitric acid, distilled water and acetone of the osch brand. The study of the composition of polyethylene revealed that the level of its contamination with elements is insignificant.

Table 3. Content of elements in filters and packaging material.

Element	micrograms per filter		mcg/g Polyethylene
	AFA-XA	FPP-15	
Na	0.47	0.1	0.57
Cr	0.1	0.3	-
Fe	3.5	7.7	-
Co	0.001	0.013	0.034
Zn	1.0	0.013	-
Se	0.002	0.003	-

Br	0.06	6.9	0.4
Sb	0.04	0.3	-
La	0.005	-	0.21
Sm	0.0015	-	-
Au	0.0005	0.0001	-
Hg	0.08	0.7	-

It should be noted that the successful application of INAA in environmental quality control requires a comprehensive study and assessment of the impact of various sources of errors, as well as an assessment of the Metrology of the developed methods.

The detection limit for INAA elements is defined as [9]

$$C_{min} = \frac{k\sqrt{I_f \cdot C_x}}{I_x} \quad (4)$$

where, C_{min} - limit of detection of the desired element;

C_x - the content of the test element in the sample;

I_x - useful activity (the area under the photo peak) of the detected element;

I_f - interfering activity (the area of the base under the peak);

k - the trust factor (3÷10).

Given (2), it is not difficult to show that

$$C_{min} = \frac{k\sqrt{I_f \cdot m_{et}}}{I_{et} \cdot V} \quad (5)$$

The reproducibility of determining elements in aerosols was evaluated as follows. Exposed filters ($S=20 \text{ cm}^2$) were divided into 8-10 equal sectors and each sector was Packed and subjected to INAA. The results obtained for the limit of determination and reproducibility of INAA according to the scheme (Fig. 1) are shown in table.4.

Table 4.

The reproducibility of the determination of elements in atmospheric aerosols of cities
($P=0.95, n=10$)

Element	The element content in the aerosols, ng/m^3	Standard deviation, S	Relative standard deviation, $S_r, \%$	Detection limit ng/m^3 , at $S_r \leq 0.33$
Na	2000	123	6,0	33
Sc	5,2	0,3	6,0	0,08
Cr	50	5,5	12	7,0
Fe	18600	2000	11	670
Co	6,4	0,6	10	0,5

Zn	680	150	22	80
As	7,0	1,7	25	1,9
Se	2,0	0,3	17	1,0
Br	215	15	7,0	2,0
Mo	70	11	16	3,0
Sb	22	2,0	9,0	1,1
Cs	3,5	0,3	8,0	1,0
La	16	1,1	7,0	0,5
Sm	2,7	0,4	16	0,05
Eu	1,1	0,13	12	0,3
Au	0,13	0,01	6,0	0,02
Hg	6,8	1,2	18	2,6
Th	3,1	0,43	14	0,34
U	0,62	0,07	12	0,1

As you can see, the values of the relative standard deviation (Sr) range from 6 to 25% for various elements. Comparatively the best reproducibility of the definition (from 6 to 10%) is achieved in INAA Sc, La, Co, Na, Br and Au. The relatively poor reproducibility (from 10 to 25%) of the definition for Se, Hg, Sm, Fe and Zn is due to the contribution of high-energy gamma lines of other radionuclides (^{24}Na , ^{82}Br), as well as the contribution of the sample matrix.

A common way to evaluate the correctness of a method is to compare the results of the analysis with the results of other independent methods or a reliable control method. Unfortunately, for most of the elements we studied in atmospheric aerosols, in the suspension of precipitation and river water, there are no reliable methods of analysis using other physical and chemical methods, the results of which could be accepted as control. Therefore, in our opinion, the most promising is the use of certified reference materials to assess and control the reproducibility and correctness of the analysis results [10].

The similarity of the physical and chemical composition of standard samples and analyzed natural objects results in the same amount of contributions to the error due to the influence of interfering reactions, the effect of self-shielding, etc. In addition, the difference in the geometric shapes of the standard and the sample is minimal, which also reduces the measurement errors of natural samples. Certified standard samples SV, SOV1-SOV5 and SP1-SP3 were used as reference samples for the analysis of aerosols, soils, waters and precipitation.

In table.5 shows our and recommended values for the content of elements in standard samples. The discrepancy between the data is on average 5-25%. Long-term and daily analysis of approved domestic and foreign standard samples indicates good reproducibility and correctness of the INAA. The productivity of INAA natural objects according to the proposed scheme is 500-600 element definitions per shift.

Table 5.

Neutron activation analysis of standard samples of natural environments (P=0,95, n=15)

Element	Recommended value	Our data	Element	Recommended value	Our data
Standard air sample (SV), mcg/g					
Na	19,8	21±3	Sb	0,4	0,36±0,05
Sc	0,99	1,1±0,2	Cs	5,0	5,2±0,5
Cr	39,6	36±4	La	4,0	4,3±0,5
Co	1,0	1,0±0,2	Sm	0,39	0,48±0,05
Se	5,0	3,9±0,5	Eu	0,05	0,06±0,01
Br	22	20±3	Au	0,049	0,05±0,01
Cd	49	44±4	Th	0,204	0,24±0,03
standard water samples (SOV1-SOV5), mg/ml					
Cr	1,0	0,8±0,2	Mo	1,0	1,3±0,2
Fe	2,0	1,8±0,2	Cd	1,0	0,9±0,2
Co	1,0	0,9±0,2	Sb	1,0	0,85±0,2
Zn	1,0	1,2±0,2	Hg	1,0	0,8±0,2
standard soil samples (SP1-SP3), mg/g					
Na	8600	9100±100	Co	14	12,5±2
K	20800	23500±2000	Zn	73	62±6
Sc	14	15,5±2	Sr	160	175±10
Cr	140	136±8	Cs	5,0	4,3±0,5
Fe	34400	29000±3000	La	37	41±5

4. Conclusion

- 1) the Recommended optimal time regimes ensured that detection limits comparable to the literature data were reached with a shorter duration of irradiation and "cooling" of samples, which is important in geophysical and environmental studies;
- 2) according to the proposed optimal scheme, concentrations and forms of finding more than twenty elements in adjacent natural environments are determined with a detection limit of 10^{-6} - 10^{-13} g/g, with a relative standard deviation of 0.05-0.25;
- 3) Analysis of metrological parameters of INAA allows us to conclude that the detection limit is low, reproducibility is satisfactory and correctness is correct, which favors the use of the method in quality control of various natural environments.

6. References

- Hoshimhujaev M. M., Kulmatov R. A., Hakimov Z. M. Study of distribution and migration of microelements in adjacent ecological environments of cities using neutron activation analysis. - Tashkent, society "Knowledge", 1992. – 20 p.
- Caldesi Yu, Claire E. Nuclear methods of chemical analysis of the environment. //edited by Myasoedov B. F., per. - M.: Chemistry, 1991. – 192 p.
- Tillaev T., Churov M. V., Chuprinin M. V. Automated gamma-spectrometers based on multi-channel analyzers "in line" with a micro-computer // TEZ. docl. 5 all-Union Sov. at activation. anal. and other radio channels. methods. - Tashkent, 1987. -1. - 92 p.
- Tustanovsky V. T. Estimation of accuracy and sensitivity of activation analysis. - M.: Atomizdat, 1976. – 192 p.
- Davidov M. G., Shcherbachenko V. A. On the optimization of instrumental activation analysis. //DEP. To the journal. Atomic energy. -1977. -№916/8679.
- Pushkin S. G., Mikhailov V. A. Comparative neutron activation analysis. Study of atmospheric aerosols. - Moscow: Nauka, 1989. – 125 p.
- Tillaev T., Churov M. V., Chuprinin M. V. Software for automated gamma-spectra based on multi-channel analyzers "in line" with a micro-computer // TEZ. Docl. 5 all-Union. No. at activation. anal. and other radio channels. methods. - Tashkent, 1987. -1. -93 p.
- Mednis I. V. Gamma radiation of radionuclides used in neutron activation analysis. Guide. – Riga: Znatne, 1987. – 210 p.
- Clauton C., Hines J.W., Elkins P.D. Detection limits with specified assurance probabilities // J. Anal. Chem. -1987. -59., N20. –2506-2514 p.
- Volberg N. sh. on periodic control of the accuracy of determining the content of impurities in the atmospheric air of cities // Tr. GGO. -1988. -467. -113-117 p.

Cite this article:

Author(s), M.HOSHUMHUJAEV¹, SH. IMOMKULOV², (2020). "Optimization of Time Modes of Neutron Activation Analysis of Natural Media Samples", **Name of the Journal:** Euro Afro Studies International Journal, (EASIJ.COM), P, 32 – 45. DOI: www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3987386, Special Issue, Issue: 2, Vol.: 2, Article: 4, Month: August, Year: 2020. Retrieved from <https://www.easij.com/all-issues/>

Published By

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International (TWCMSI)

